

Quality and Continuum
of Maternal and Newborn Care
in the sub-Saharan African Region
during the first year
of the COVID-19 pandemic

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Abstract

Background

Sub-Saharan Africa is the region of the world with the highest rates of maternal and newborn mortality. Most of these maternal and newborn deaths are attributed to poor quality of care and inequities in access to maternal and newborn health services. Maintaining good quality of care before, during and after childbirth can save the lives of women and newborn babies. The COVID-19 pandemic and associated outbreak control measures affecting health systems have pose considerable challenges for countries to maintain the provision of high quality, essential maternal and newborn health services. Consequently, this pandemic might have aggravated the previously compromised state of maternal and newborn service delivery in sub-Saharan Africa. This study explores maternal and newborn health care professionals' perceptions and experiences on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care provision in the sub-Saharan African region.

Methods

This is a secondary analysis of data obtained from the second round of a repeated global online survey of health professionals directly involved with the provision of maternal and newborn care during the COVID-19 pandemic. This cross-sectional study was conducted from July to December 2020, and the survey included both close- and open-ended questions. In this analysis, we only included responses from healthcare providers who reported working in any sub-Saharan African country.

Results

A total of 94 health professionals practicing 13 sub-Saharan African countries were included in this study. Both negative and positive impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic

on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care were reported. The main negative findings from the analysis of close-ended questions included a decrease in the number of women accessing antenatal (56% of respondents) and intrapartum care (45%), increased time spacing between antenatal care appointments (47%), decrease in the number of beds on the ward due to social distancing measures (27%), reduction in the number of visitors permitted in the postnatal ward (67%) and shortened visiting hours allowed for postpartum women (39%). Other major negative consequences related to the content of care included reduction in the number of routine checks conducted during pregnancy (66%), shortened duration of consultations (42%), reduced number of allowed birth companions/banning of birth companions in health facilities (31%), and earlier discharge from the health facilities following birth (54%). Four themes identified from the analysis of open-ended questions which illustrated some positive impacts that accompanied the pandemic included improved infection prevention and control and water hygiene and sanitation measures in health facilities, adaptation of service provision, improved knowledge on COVID-19 among healthcare providers and improved provider-to-woman communication.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic and its associated mitigation measures had both negative and positive impacts on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care provision in the sub-Saharan African region. Our study thus highlights the need to strike a balance between implementing mitigating measures and ensuring the continuous delivery of quality maternal and newborn services during pandemics while improving health systems' resilience and preparedness to face subsequent health system shocks.

1 Introduction

Quality of maternal and newborn care, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is “*the degree to which maternal and newborn health services increase the likelihood of timely, appropriate care for the purpose of achieving desired outcomes that are both consistent with current professional knowledge and take into account the preferences and aspirations of individual women and their families*” (1). This study seeks to understand how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care in the sub-Saharan African region from the perspective of maternal and newborn health professionals.

Sub-Saharan Africa is the region of the world which suffers the highest rates of maternal and newborn mortality (2,3). More than half of the global maternal deaths occur in this region (2). Even though the majority of these deaths are preventable, progress in reducing maternal and neonatal deaths has been slowest in the region (2,4). The persistently high death rates recorded in sub-Saharan Africa have been attributed to poor quality of care and inequities in access to maternal and newborn health services (2,5-8). To be able to meet the SDG 3.1 and 3.2 targets (reduce maternal mortality to less than 70 per 100,000 live births and newborn mortality to as low as 12 per 1,000 live births) in the region by 2030, quality and access to maternal and newborn health services need to improve. The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted on the delivery of (essential) health services worldwide (9). It poses considerable challenges for countries to maintain the provision of high quality, essential maternal and newborn health services (10).

Restrictions imposed on the health system and the population in general due to the pandemic, including lockdowns, bans on public transport, curfews, and reassignment of health personnel to COVID-19 units, have led to decreased accessibility and availability of healthcare services. Other adaptations implemented by health systems globally, such as providing care remotely (telemedicine), physical distancing between women and providers and separation of mothers and newborns have significant impacts on the quality of maternal and newborn care delivery (9). Consequently, the pandemic might have aggravated the previously compromised state of maternal and newborn service delivery in sub-Saharan Africa. It is therefore important to assess the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn health service delivery in the region.

Pregnancy, delivery, and postpartum represent critical periods in a woman's life (11,12). Childbirth and the first week postpartum are the time of greatest risk for mothers and their children as most maternal and newborn complications present during this period (13,14). About a third of all neonatal deaths occur within 24 hours after birth, and close to three-quarters occur within one week of life (3). Children who die within the first 28 days of birth usually suffer from conditions and diseases associated with lack of quality care at or immediately after delivery and in the first days of life (3). Quality of care is a central concern in health systems to sustainably improve the health status of a population. There is a complex relationship between quality of healthcare and expected health outcomes (15). Maintaining a good quality of care throughout the antenatal, intrapartum

(labor, childbirth) and immediate postpartum period is essential to avert maternal and newborn mortality and other undesirable outcomes of pregnancy such as stillbirths and birth trauma (2,12,16). All women need access to antenatal care during pregnancy, to skilled care during childbirth, and to appropriate care and support in the weeks that follow immediately postpartum(2). It is particularly important that all births are attended by skilled health professionals in an enabling environment, as timely management and treatment can make the difference between life and death for both the mother and the baby(2). After delivery, newborns should receive immediate newborn care, which includes thermal care (drying and wrapping, skin-to-skin care, delayed bathing), hygienic cord care and early initiation of breastfeeding. These practices can be promoted at the facility, community, and household levels through a variety of channels including through postnatal home visits(4). The four recommended postnatal care contacts delivered at health facility or through home visits play a key role to reach these newborns and their families(17). Therefore, to improve maternal and newborn health, barriers that limit access to quality maternal health services must be identified and addressed at all levels of the health system(2).

Since early 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has posed major challenges to health care delivery in many settings(18,19). This pandemic has had both direct and indirect impacts on health and wellbeing of pregnant women and newborns(20). Regarding the direct effects of the SARS-CoV-2 infection on maternal and newborn health, although pregnant do not seem to be at higher risk of acquiring the virus, when infected, pregnant women present with more serious disease, which can be associated with an increased likelihood of preterm birth, still-birth and small-for-gestational-age babies(21,22). Vertical transmission of the

virus to newborn babies is very rare, and babies who develop symptoms tend to recover quickly (21). Indirect effects of the pandemic on the other hand can lead to substantial increases in maternal and newborn morbidity and mortality(19,22). The indirect impacts of COVID-19 were estimated to reach up to a 38.6% increase in maternal mortality, and 44.7% increase in child mortality per month across 118 low- and middle-income countries(23). Pandemic control policies such as lockdowns, repurposing of health facilities for COVID-19 care, and closure of primary health services have resulted in limited access to essential health services. This has disrupted the continuum of care, as many routine and elective services have been suspended(9,18,20).

Most studies assessing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality of maternal and newborn care provision revealed a negative impact. Some of these findings include inadequate emotional and physical support for women during labor and breast feeding, delayed initiation of breastfeeding for newborns, discontinuation of kangaroo mother care, separation of suspected/confirmed COVID-19 positive women from their newborns, increased exposure of women and newborns to medically unjustified procedures (for example caesarean sections and labor inductions), insufficient involvement of women in decision-making about their care, unclear communication from staff, and earlier discharge of women and newborns from health facilities(24-28). Some positive findings reported in a few studies include capacity-building for health workers through training, motivation and psychological support, and the use of telemedicine to support service provision(29,30).

Even though much progress has been made in increasing coverage of in-facility deliveries during the past two decades, reduction in maternal and neonatal mortality remains slow. Therefore, attention has shifted to the quality of care (1).

“Good quality of care requires appropriate use of effective clinical and non-clinical interventions, strengthened health infrastructure and optimum skills and attitude of health providers, resulting in improved health outcomes and positive experience for women and providers. Moreover, quality of care is considered a key component of the right to health, and the route to equity and dignity for women and children” (31).

Frameworks that focus on the needs of women and their newborns have been developed to ensure they receive high-quality of care throughout pregnancy, childbirth and the postnatal period. One of these frameworks is the World Health Organization's (WHO) framework for quality of care, which has eight elements:

- (1) evidence-based practices for routine care and management of complications,
- (2) actionable information systems,
- (3) functional referral systems,
- (4) effective communication,
- (5) respect and dignity,
- (6) emotional support,
- (7) competent and motivated human resources, and
- (8) essential physical resources available (1).

Another framework is the Lancet Quality of Maternal and Newborn Care framework designed as part of a midwifery series, which has five main components (Practice categories, Organization of care, Values, Philosophy and Care provider components) and several sub-components. These frameworks present the scope of care to which all women and newborns should have access, and which can contribute to improving health outcomes.

The impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on quality of maternal and newborn care in the sub-Saharan African region are not well known. To the best of our knowledge, there are no existing regional studies from sub-Saharan Africa looking at the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality of maternal and newborn health from the points of view and experiences of health

professionals in the field. Additionally, little is known about any positive impacts of the pandemic in relation to maternal and newborn health in the region.

This study thus explored both the negative and positive indirect impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care provision in sub-Saharan Africa, from the angle of health professionals. Results from the study were intended to fill knowledge gaps, and to generate evidence that gives the basis to recommendations geared towards improving the quality of maternal and newborn service delivery during the present and future pandemics.

Study design

This is a cross-sectional mixed-methods study of maternal and newborn health professionals.

pandemic(36,37). The second round of the survey took place from July to December 2020. Data collection was performed through self-administered online questionnaires using the KoBoToolbox.

Study setting

Sub-Saharan Africa is the region of the world which records the highest number of childbirths (total fertility rate is 4.7 children per woman) (32-34). Women in sub-Saharan Africa, on average, have many more pregnancies than women in high-income countries, and they face the highest lifetime risk of death due to pregnancy (1 in 38) (2,35). Maternal and neonatal mortality remains highest in this region(2,4). Children born in sub-Saharan Africa present with 10 times more risk of death in the first month after birth compared to children born in high-income countries(4). In 2019, the estimated maternal mortality ratio in the region was 533 deaths per 100,000 live births, while the estimated neonatal mortality rate was 27 deaths per 1,000 live births (3,17,35). These high rates of maternal and newborn deaths are mainly due to lack of and inequitable access to quality maternal and newborn care.

Survey questionnaire

A questionnaire was developed in English by a multi-disciplinary team of international experts in maternal, sexual and reproductive health, health systems, epidemiology, sociology, anthropology, and clinical practice. This questionnaire was then piloted by asking five maternal and newborn health professionals from different settings to complete the questionnaire and provide feedback, which was used to assess face validity and refine the wording of questions and response options. After piloting, the questionnaire was translated into 11 other languages by experts fluent in these languages. The languages in which the questionnaire was available which are relevant to respondents from sub-Saharan Africa are English, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Kiswahili and Arabic. The questionnaire included questions on respondents' background, preparedness for COVID-19, response to COVID-19 and own work experience during the pandemic. All respondents were then invited to participate in an optional module that asked about adaptations to various care processes and respondents' perceptions regarding changes in the uptake of care by women and newborns.

Data source and data collection

This study used secondary data obtained from the second round of a repeated global online survey of maternal and newborn healthcare providers, conducted during the first year of the COVID-19

In the first round of the survey, the optional module of the questionnaire included only open-ended questions intended for participants to respond with free text(37).

In the second round of the survey, this module was modified (based on responses obtained from Round 1) to include more structured questions (format of “select all responses which apply”) and some open-ended (free text) questions. Details of the questionnaire (questions and provided response options) in the optional module section of the survey are in Table 1.

Study participants and sampling

Study participants were recruited using various maternal and newborn networks and social media platforms to attain a large sample size. Sampling was non-random due to unavailability of a global sampling frame for the study population. All health professionals directly involved with providing maternal and newborn care during the COVID-19 pandemic who consented to participate in the survey, were eligible for inclusion in the global study. From the total survey participants, those from sub-Saharan Africa who responded to the optional module section (Effect of COVID-19 on the provision of maternal and newborn care) of the survey were included in this current analysis.

Variables and definitions

This study uses variables derived from the section of the questionnaire looking at respondents' background characteristics in order to describe the sample. These variables included: country where respondent is based, profession/cadre, type of service provided, level of healthcare institution and type of organization where respondent works, and type of geographical area.

Antenatal care: this is a type of preventive healthcare, provided in the form of outpatient medical checkups. It is a means to identify high-risk pregnancies and educate women so that they might experience a healthier delivery and outcome. Responses about adaptations to antenatal care during the study period were obtained from questions 1 and 5 (Table 1).

Intrapartum care: this is the period spanning labor and childbirth. It is the care provided (to women and newborns) from the onset of labor through delivery of the placenta. Responses about childbirth care were obtained from questions 2 and 6 (Table 1).

Postnatal care: this is care given to the mother and her newborn baby immediately after the delivery of the placenta and during the following six weeks. Inpatient postnatal care is the care provided to mothers and newborns hospitalized at the health facility after childbirth, while outpatient postnatal care is care provided to mothers and newborns following discharge from the health facility either through routine outpatient visits to the facility or through home visits. Responses about postnatal care were obtained from questions 3,4,7 and 8 (Table 1).

Positive impacts: These were the changes made either by the respondent or changes to the respondent's facility/working environment, which, in their opinion, succeeded to improve the provision or quality of maternal and newborn care during the COVID-19 pandemic. These were obtained through free-text responses to an open-ended question (Question 9, Table 1).

Table 1: The effect of COVID-19 on the provision of maternal and newborn care

Optional module: Effect of COVID-19 on the provision of maternal and newborn care		
Q #	Question	Response
1	In the past month, how was outpatient antenatal care affected? Please select all that apply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suspended provision completely for some or all of the time - Shorter operating hours or reduced number of days care is available - Appointments scheduled further apart for consecutive patients - Group classes or group counselling sessions suspended - Prioritising women with high-risk pregnancies with face-to-face care - Unable to see all patients who need care in person - Use of technology to provide care - Number of women accessing antenatal care decreased - Fees charged for antenatal care decreased - Fees charged for antenatal care increased - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
2	In the past month, how was inpatient intrapartum / childbirth care affected? Please select all that apply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suspended provision completely for some or all of the time - Shorter operating hours or reduced number of days care is available - Reduced space on the labour ward due to creation of COVID-19 isolation rooms / spaces - Reduced number of beds due to social distancing measures - Reduced number of women accessing facility childbirth care - Increased demand for home-based childbirth care - Screening or testing birth companions for COVID-19 - Designating a circuit/pathway specific for COVID-19 suspected/confirmed women - Fees charged for childbirth care decreased - Fees charged for childbirth care increased - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
3	In the past month, how was inpatient postnatal care for women and newborns affected? Please select all that apply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suspended provision completely for some or all of the time - Shorter operating hours or reduced number of days care is available - Reduced space on the postnatal ward due to creation of COVID-19 isolation rooms/ spaces - Dedicated neonatal cots/equipment for newborns born to COVID-19 mothers - Reduced number of beds due to social distancing measures - Reduced number of allowed visitors - Visitors banned - Shortened visiting hours - Parents not allowed to visit newborn in newborn intensive care units (NICU) - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
4	In the past month, how was outpatient postnatal care for women and newborns affected? Please select all that apply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suspended provision completely for some or all of the time - Shorter operating hours or reduced number of days care is available - Prioritising highest need patients only - Appointments scheduled further apart for consecutive patients - Unable to see all patients in person - Use of technology to provide care - Reduced number of women/newborns accessing care - Home-based visits reduced or stopped - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
Next, we would like to ask about changes you noticed in the content of care.		
5	In the past month, was the content of antenatal care provided by you or in your facility affected in terms of: (select all that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fewer routine visits or checks conducted during pregnancy - Reduced availability of routine tests - Denial of care to women or babies with suspected/confirmed cases with COVID-19 - Less time spent during consultation to reduce contact time with women - Counselling women to prepare for self-care (for example, measuring their own blood pressure) - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
6	In the past month, was the content of intrapartum / childbirth care provided by you or in your facility affected in terms of:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unable to regularly assess progress of labour - Staff limiting duration of close contact with patients - Decreased elective caesarean sections - Increase in inductions of labour - Increase in labour augmentation practices - Reduced availability of pain relief options - Unable to provide or support home births - Reduced availability of equipment, supplies or medications

	(select all that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced availability of laboratory testing - Reduced the number of birth companions allowed - Birth companions banned for all women - COVID-19 positive or suspected women delivered only by caesarean section - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
7	In the past month, was the content of inpatient postnatal care to women and newborns provided by you or in your facility affected in terms of: (select all that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shorter length of stay in facility / earlier discharge - Less frequent routine postnatal monitoring in the facility - Reduced / suspended newborn vaccination or screening - Limited skin-to-skin contact between newborn and mother - Delayed initiation of breastfeeding - COVID-19 suspected or positive mothers: separating mother and baby - COVID-19 suspected or positive mothers: breastfeeding not allowed or discouraged - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
8	In the past month, was the content of outpatient postnatal care to women and newborns provided by you or in your facility affected in terms of: (select all that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced/ suspended breastfeeding support - Reduced/suspended postpartum family planning counselling / provision - Reduced/ suspended newborn vaccination - Reduced/ suspended newborn weight monitoring - Reduced/ suspended mental health monitoring and support to women - Reduced/ suspended social care support or referral - Reduced duration or content of home-based visits - Other changes or comments on responses selected above (please describe)
9	Were there any changes made by you or your facility that you think succeeded in improving the provision or quality of maternal and newborn care during the COVID-19 pandemic? Please tell us about them [free text]	

COVID-19 Maternity Survey - Round 2

▼ Online Questionnaire

Please click the box above to choose another **language**
 Veuillez cliquer la case ci-dessus pour choisir une autre **langue**
 الرجاء الضغط على المربع أعلاه لإختيار لغة أخرى
 Per scegliere un'altra **lingua**, puo' cliccare sul link qui sopra
 Klik op het menu hierboven om een andere **taal** te kiezen
 Bitte klicken Sie hier, um eine andere **Sprache** zu wählen
 Clique na caixa acima para escolher outro **idioma**
 右上のボックスから言語を選択してください
 Bitte klicken Sie hier, um eine andere **Sprache** zu wählen
 Tafadhali bonyeza kiboksi hapo juu kuchagua **lugha** nyingine
 Пожалуйста, нажмите на поле сверху страницы, чтобы выбрать другой **язык**
 Por favor haga 'clíc' en la parte superior para escoger un **idioma** diferente

First page of the online survey (July 2020)

Data processing and analysis

Data were exported from the online server to Microsoft Excel and cleaned. In this sub-analysis, aside from English, French was the only other language used by participants to provide responses. French text responses to the optional module questions were first translated to English by using Google translate before content analysis. The impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care were analyzed sequentially with respect to the various components of maternal and newborn care (antenatal, intrapartum, and postnatal care). Additionally, a separate analysis of the positive impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic was performed.

Quantitative analysis for this study involved descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) using Microsoft Excel. A qualitative thematic analysis of free-text responses was conducted, whereby responses were read, and codes were generated and assigned to corresponding pieces of text based on the analysis of their content. These codes were then grouped into common themes to reflect respondents' perception about changes in the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care in their facilities.

Qualitative data allowed for the emergence of alternative pathways of impact not considered among the pre-set response categories in the quantitative survey. In addition, they provided further context and insight into some of the survey responses, hence enriching the data.

Ethical considerations

This study involves secondary analysis of data collected in 2020 and archived for further explorative analysis. The primary study received ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board at the Institute of Tropical Medicine (approval number: 1372/2020). Participants were provided with information about the study, and they gave consent online before participating in the study by checking a box affirming their voluntarily participation. No personal identifiers were used while reporting the findings from this secondary analysis.

3 Results

A total of 1,248 maternal and newborn health workers participated in the second round of the global survey, 192 (15%) of which were from sub-Saharan Africa. Among these participants, 106 consented to the optional module section of the survey, but only 94 (49%) participants from 13 countries were included in the final analysis (Table 2). Participants who consented but did not provide responses (n=6), participants who were not directly providing maternal and newborn care (n=4), and participant responses with more than 90% missing across survey items (n=2) were excluded. Of the participants included in this analysis, 35 (37%) were obstetricians - gynecologists, 38 (40%) were medical doctors with no specialization, 9 (10%) were midwives, 8 (9%) were nurses, 3 (3%) were pediatricians or neonatologists, and 1 (1%) was a resident in obstetrics and gynecology.

Most of these participants worked in public health facilities at various levels (37% at the national level, 32% at the university or teaching facilities, 10% at district level or lower); mostly located in large cities (57%) (Table 3).

In terms of the health facility of primary employment, most participants practiced at referral hospitals (51%), followed by regional/district hospitals (14%). The main maternal and newborn health services provided by the respondents' facilities were inpatient intrapartum care (60%), inpatient postnatal care (64%), outpatient postnatal care (55%), family planning provision and counselling (56%), outpatient antenatal care (55%), and surgical care (50%). Other services less commonly provided included neonatal care for small and sick newborns (27%), outpatient breastfeeding support (27%), and home-based childbirth care (14%).

Table 2: Country of practice of study participants

	Name of Country	Number of participants from country n= 94 (100%)
1.	Benin	1 (1)
2.	Cameroon	15 (16)
3.	Democratic Republic of Congo	30 (32)
4.	Ethiopia	1 (1)
5.	Guinea	4 (4)
6.	Kenya	5 (5)
7.	Malawi	1 (1)
8.	Nigeria	18 (19)
9.	Rwanda	1 (1)
10.	South Africa	3 (3)
11.	United republic of Tanzania	6 (6)
12.	Uganda	6 (6)
13.	Zambia	3 (3)

Table 3: Background characteristics of study participants

Background characteristics of study participants	Number of participants n=94 (%)
Profession	
Medical doctor (no specialization)	38 (40)
Obstetrician/gynecologist	35 (37)
Midwives	9 (10)
Nurses	8 (9)
Pediatrician/neonatologist	3 (3)
Resident obstetrician	1 (1)
Type of services provided (Multiple responses allowed)	
Outpatient antenatal care	52 (55)
Inpatient antenatal care	55 (59)
Outpatient (home-based) childbirth care	13 (14)
Inpatient childbirth (intrapartum) care	56 (60)
Inpatient postnatal care	60 (64)
Outpatient postnatal care	52 (55)
Outpatient breastfeeding support	25 (27)
Surgical care	47 (50)
Neonatal care for small and sick newborns	25 (27)
Family planning provision and counselling	53 (56)
Post-abortion care	48 (51)
Community outreach	24 (26)
Home visits	8 (9)
Level of health institution of the primary job of the participant	
Referral hospital	48 (51)
District/regional hospital	13 (14)
Polyclinic or Clinic	9 (10)
Health center	7 (7)
Independent/self-practicing	3 (3)
Dispensary	2 (2)
Health post/unit	1 (1)
other	11 (12)
Organization type	
Public (national level)	35 (37)
Public (university or teaching facility)	30 (32)
Public (district level or below)	9 (10)
Private not-for-profit	7 (7)
Faith-based or mission	4 (4)
Independent/self-practicing	3 (3)
Non-governmental	2 (2)
Private for profit	2 (2)
others	2 (2)
Type of geographical area of facility	
Large city (more than 1 million inhabitants)	54 (57)
Small city (100,000 to 1 million inhabitants)	20 (21)
Town (less than 100,000 inhabitants)	6 (6)
Village/rural area	13 (14)
Unknown	1 (1)

Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the provision of outpatient antenatal care

Regarding outpatient antenatal care (ANC) provision, the main influences of COVID-19 reported by respondents were a decrease in the number of women accessing antenatal care (56%), an increase in the spacing of antenatal care appointments (47%), prioritization of face-to-face care for women with high-risk pregnancies (30%), suspension of group counselling for women (28%), and a decrease in the operating hours and the number of days available for antenatal care provision in their facilities (25%). Other impacts of COVID-19 less frequently reported were inability to see all patients who needed care in person (15%), partial or complete suspension of ANC service in facilities (13%), decrease in the fees charged for ANC (11%), use of technology to provide care (7%), and increase in the fees charged for ANC (1%). Additional analysis of open-ended responses provided by 6 participants revealed other consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic such as a reduction in the number of personnel available to provide antenatal care (n=2) and a decrease in the participation of the (male) partners of the women during ANC (n=1). Some respondents noted that COVID-19 had no impact on ANC provision in their facilities (n=3).

Analysis of the changes related to the content of ANC provided revealed fewer routine visits or checks conducted during pregnancy (66%), shortening of consultation time to reduce contact with women (42%) and reduced availability of routine test (23%), as the main changes. Other changes recorded from the open-ended responses included reservation of care provision for slightly more experienced staff (n=1) and withdrawal of trainees from the health care facilities (n=1). Some respondents also reported no change in the content of ANC (n=5).

Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the provision of intrapartum care

The most frequently reported impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on intrapartum care provision included a decrease in the number of women accessing facilities for intrapartum care (45%), a decrease in the number of beds on the ward due to social distancing measures (27%), and shorter operating hours or reduced number of days available to provide care (18%). Other impacts of the pandemic reported include the designation of a specific circuit/pathway for COVID-19 suspected/confirmed women (12%), decreased fees charged for childbirth care (10%), reduced space on the labor ward due to creation of COVID-19 isolation rooms or spaces (9%), increased fees charged for childbirth care (9%), increased demand for home-based childbirth care (7%), partial or complete suspension of intrapartum care provision (5%), and compulsory screening/testing of birth companions for COVID-19 (2%). From the analysis of the open-ended responses, one participant reported that women were not allowed to be accompanied by their partners/ birth companions during delivery in their facility, while other participants reported no change in the provision of intrapartum care in their facilities during the pandemic (n=5).

The main changes to the content of the intrapartum care provided were limited duration of close staff contact with women (36%), reduced number of allowed birth companions (31%), banning of birth companions (20%) and shortage of equipment, supplies or medications (20%). Free text responses provided by respondents include decreased availability of personal protective equipment (n=1), inability of clients to access care due to lockdown measures and restrictions on public transport (n=1), increased emergency caesarean section rates (n=1)

and delay arrival at health facility during labor due to an aversion of public health services by women (n=1). Three respondents also reported no change in the content of intrapartum care.

Impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on the provision of inpatient postnatal care

The main changes to the provision of inpatient postnatal care reported by study participants were a reduction in the number of visitors permitted in the ward (67%), shortened visiting hours (39%) and reduced number of beds available in the ward due to social distancing measures (23%). Few participants also reported other changes such as shorter operating hours and reduced number of days available to provide care (19%), partial or complete suspension of care (12%), reduced space on the postnatal ward due to creation of COVID-19 isolation rooms/spaces (11%), parents not being allowed to visit newborns in the newborn intensive care unit (11%), dedicating neonatal cots/equipment for babies born to COVID-19 positive mothers (7%) and complete banning of visitors from the inpatient postnatal ward (7%). The six respondents who provided open-ended

answers reported that there were no changes to inpatient postnatal care provision in their facilities.

Major changes to the content of inpatient postnatal care recorded were a decrease in the length of stay of women at the facility/earlier discharge (54%) and less frequent routine postnatal monitoring in the health facility (40%). Other responses mentioned via free text include prohibition of breastfeeding among mothers with confirmed COVID-19 whose babies were admitted in the neonatal unit until after 14 days of isolation (n=1), implementation of COVID-19 barrier measures (n=1), and no change in the content of inpatient postnatal care (n=9).

Impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on outpatient postnatal care provision

Most respondents reported increased spacing of outpatient postnatal appointment schedules (48%), decreased access to care for women and newborns (38%), and prioritization of highest need patients only (37%) as consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the provision of outpatient postnatal care in their facilities. Respondents also described inability to see all patients in person (20%), suspension of care (17%), shortened duration for care provision (16%), decreased home visits (14%), and the use of technology to provide care (10%) as other consequences of the pandemic.

The most frequently reported impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the content of outpatient postnatal care were reduced/suspended postpartum family planning counselling and provision (34%), reduced duration and content of home visits (28%), reduced/suspended newborn weight monitoring (21%) and reduced/suspended social care support (20%). Other findings included reduced

newborn vaccination (16%), reduced mental health monitoring (16%), and reduced breastfeeding support (7%). One respondent in the open-ended section reported that care provision in their facility was subject to availability of appropriate PPE, while other respondents reported that the pandemic had no effect on the content of outpatient postnatal care.

Poster in a hospital maternity ward, Conakry, Guinea. February 2022.

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Changes made to improve the provision and quality of maternal and newborn care during the COVID-19 pandemic

This was an open-ended question (question 9) to which 42 participants responded with 47 free text responses. In total, four themes were identified during the analysis of this section. The two themes which were commonly reported included improved IPC (infection prevention and control) and WASH (water, sanitation, and hygiene), and adaptations to health service provision. Two less commonly reported themes were improved knowledge on COVID-19, and improved provider-client communication.

Improved IPC and WASH

Most of the participants who responded to question 9 (n=22) reported enforcement of barrier measures in their facilities such as compulsory use of mask and other personal protective equipment, social/physical distancing, restriction of number of visitors and trainees in the facility, instituting home visits to reduce overcrowding at the facility and regular hand washing and sanitizing between patients. Some participants also reported the practice of compulsory COVID-19 screening of women upon entry into the maternity unit, regular disinfection of the entire facility, preparation of hand sanitizers and installation of hydro-alcoholic gel dispensers at various points in their facilities.

Adaptations to health service provision/delivery

Sixteen respondents reported some changes in the way services were being delivered at their facilities during the COVID-19 pandemic. Some of these changes included:

- Reorganization of work teams and readjustment of work schedules for the facility workers.

“It was mainly in the nursing and Midwifery department, Nurses staying in the hospital compound volunteered to cover more duties than their counterparts staying out. When the lockdown eased, transport challenges still persist and they agreed amongst themselves, (knowing how far they stayed and how they got to work) on how to cover the duties and it seems to work well. Some opted for straight night duties, while some opted for straight day duties. Voluntary annual leave other than sick leave was suspended for doctors, which made more doctors available, hence no burn out for the few doctors.”

(Obstetrician/gynecologist, referral hospital, Uganda)

- Changes in the way clients were being followed-up/continuity of care

“We managed to provide a one stop shop for postnatal care by getting all role players to provide services on the same day i.e., on a Wednesday- pediatrician, psychologist (for postnatal mental issues), dietician (for feeding practice and breastfeeding support), audiology, immunization- all in one place.”

(Pediatrician, referral hospital, South Africa)

- Other adaptations to service provision/delivery such as improved triage of patients in the facilities based on their suspected infection status, provision of psychosocial counseling to women in the context of COVID-19, increase in the

number of days of postnatal care provision, reduction of the cost of care, provision of transportation fare to women seeking services, and the use of telemedicine to render services to clients.

Improved knowledge of COVID-19

Five participants reported to have received education and training sessions on COVID-19 prevention and management of cases.

Improved provider-client communication

Four respondents reported improvement in the communication between service providers and the (women) clients.

“Introducing a phone and phone number for each obstetric sub-unit and making it available for the patients to call us on”.

(Obstetrician/gynecologist, referral hospital, Nigeria)

4 Discussion

The objective of this study was to explore the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care in sub-Saharan Africa by assessing health providers' perceptions and experiences through an online survey during the period July-December 2020. This study benefited from both quantitative and qualitative responses.

We identified both negative and positive impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care in the sub-Saharan African region. One of the main negative impacts of the pandemic was a decrease in the number of patients accessing maternal and newborn services, which commonly affected the entire continuum of care provision (antenatal, intrapartum and outpatient postnatal care). Increased spacing of appointments and prioritization of in-person care for highest-need clients were mainly reported with antenatal and outpatient postnatal care, whereas a reduction in the length of time available for care provision was mainly an issue with antenatal and intrapartum care. A decrease in the number of beds available on the ward due to social distancing was also a common main finding reported for intrapartum and inpatient postnatal care provision. Other frequently reported negative consequences of the pandemic were suspension of antenatal care group counselling for women, limited number of visitors permitted and shortened visiting hours in the inpatient postnatal ward. Impacts related to the content of care included reduction in the number of routine checks conducted during pregnancy, shortened duration of consultations, reduced number of allowed birth companions or banning of birth companions in the facilities,

less frequent monitoring of women and newborns, earlier discharge from the facility, reduced/ suspended postnatal family planning counselling and provision, and reduced duration and content of home visits. Shortage of routine test, equipment, supplies, and medications was another issue noted during the pandemic.

Regarding the positive impacts of the pandemic, the four themes identified in this study were improved IPC and WASH in health facilities, adaptation of service provision, improved knowledge on COVID-19 and improved provider-client communication. In the next section, we will discuss how these findings impacted on quality of maternal and newborn care provision. We will use the Lancet quality of maternal and newborn care framework (Figure 1) to summarize these impacts. This framework was identified after an explorative search of the literature for relevant and operationalized frameworks of quality of maternal and newborn care because of its broad scope, which fits the exploratory nature of this study.

Most of the main findings reported in this study suggested a negative influence of COVID-19 on the practice categories of the Quality of Maternal and Newborn Care (QMNC) framework. Findings such as decreased access to maternal and newborn services, shorter operating hours, and inability to see all those who needed care might have compromised the care planning aspect of the practice category. In addition, findings like increased spacing of antenatal and postnatal appointments, decreased number of beds, decreased postnatal family planning counselling and provision, earlier discharge from the postnatal ward, and decreased duration and content of home visits can compromise the promotion of

normal processes. All these aspects of the practice categories of the QMNC framework are important first to prevent complications of pregnancy and childbirth, and then to manage these complications if they arise. Shortage of routine tests, equipment, supplies and medications could compromise the organization of care component of the QMNC framework, while banning of birth companions, and restrictions on the number of visitors permitted in the postnatal ward might compromise the social aspect of the philosophy component of the QMNC framework. Organization of care component is relevant to ensure smooth delivery of services leading to better outcomes, while social support reduces stress and improves emotional/ mental wellbeing of women.

Most of the positive findings such as improved IPC and WASH, adaptations to service provision/delivery and improved knowledge on the COVID-19 pandemic reported in our study might positively influence the organization of care component of the QMNC framework, while the enhanced provider-client communication could influence the “value” component. The improvement in providers' knowledge on COVID-19 reported in our study could be due to the timing of the study (July-Dec 2020) – showing that facilities and systems had some time to gather and disseminate knowledge about the disease, in contrast to the early days of the onset of the pandemic – when little knowledge was available

Figure 1. Lancet Quality of Maternal and Newborn Care Framework(37)

Source: The Lancet, Vol.384, Renfrew et al., Midwifery and quality care: findings from a new evidence-informed framework for maternal and newborn care

Some explanations provided by participants in the open-ended responses for the decreased access to maternal and newborn services by women included lockdown measures, transport disruptions and aversion of health facilities during the pandemic. These explanations are in line with literature published elsewhere(12,18,39,40).

Fear of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus at health facilities was the main reason provided in the literature for the aversion of health facilities. For instance, a qualitative study on the experience of indigent mothers and health care providers during the COVID-19 pandemic conducted in Kilifi county in Kenya reported a drop in access to maternal health services due to women's fear of contracting the SARS-CoV-2 virus at health facilities(11). Moreover, several of our findings regarding decreased utilization of services during the COVID-19 pandemic resemble those obtained from three other studies conducted in sub-Saharan Africa. The first study concerned a multi-country empirical assessment of health service utilization during the COVID-19 pandemic with a focus on maternal, newborn and child health services. This study was conducted by using routine health facility data, during a similar study period (March to December 2020) (41). The second study is an analysis from eight sub-Saharan African countries on the disruption of maternal and child health services utilization during COVID-19 from March to July 2020(19). The third study conducted a mini review on the impact of COVID-19 on maternal health care in Africa(42). All these studies noted a decline in the utilization of antenatal care services, institutional deliveries, postnatal services, and newborn immunization services.

Routine antenatal and postnatal care are important to prevent or identify and treat conditions that may threaten the health of the fetus/newborn and/or the mother, and to help a woman approach pregnancy, birth

and beyond as positive experiences. The WHO recommends a minimum of eight antenatal contacts to increase the likelihood of receiving effective maternal health interventions during pregnancy(43). Antenatal consultations are also the ideal location to establish birth plans which can ensure that childbirth takes place in safe circumstances with skilled attendants. Additionally, all women and newborns require regular postnatal checkups in the first 6 weeks after delivery, with a minimum of three consultations recommended after the immediate postnatal period.

Failure to comply with these standards might have left less opportunity for the identification and adequate management of conditions or events that could negatively impact the health of mother and/or fetus/newborn during pregnancy or delivery. Home-based newborn-care interventions have also been shown to improve coverage of key newborn-care practices, such as early initiation of breastfeeding, exclusive breastfeeding, skin-to-skin contact, delayed bathing and attention to hygiene (washing hands with soap and water and clean umbilical cord care). Therefore, as a complementary strategy to facility-based postnatal care, WHO and UNICEF now recommend home visits by skilled professionals during the baby's first week of life to improve newborn survival(44).

Part of the main findings from this study includes increased spacing of antenatal appointments (resulting in fewer total number of antenatal contacts during pregnancy), or a direct reduction in the number of routine checks conducted during pregnancy (sometimes for women without risk factors only), shortened length of consultations, reduced time available for care provision, less frequent monitoring of women and newborns, earlier discharge from the facility. These changes could have led to a compromise in the quality of antenatal and postnatal care provision. Some open-ended responses provided by

participants that could explain these limitations in antenatal and postnatal care provision were a reduction in the number of staff available to provide these services during the pandemic and the permission of only slightly more experienced staff to provide care during this period. These explanations are in line with reports from the World Health Organization "pulse survey" which noted a disruption in the provision of some services in health facilities due to redeployment of staff from other units to provide care to patients with COVID-19 (39,40).

Other findings such as suspension of postnatal family planning counselling and provision could have significant negative consequences in the short- and long-term. Family planning is a critical element for improving maternal and health, as reducing the number of pregnancies (especially unintended pregnancies) in turn reduces the risk of maternal deaths. A comparative cross-sectional study on the impact of COVID-19 on utilization and outcome of reproductive, maternal, and newborn health services at governmental health facilities in South West Ethiopia, conducted in 2020 also revealed a significant reduction in utilization of family planning services during the pandemic(45).

Lastly, some positive impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the provision of maternal and newborn services, such as adaptations of the work schedule of health facility workers and the use of telemedicine were similarly to findings reported from a study on the adaptations implemented for maternal, newborn and child Health service provision during the early phase of the COVID-19 pandemic conducted in Lagos, Nigeria(29).

Limitations

Sampling bias and lack of representativeness: sampling carried out in this study was non-randomized convenience sampling, thus, the study was prone to selection bias. Additionally, the sample size included in this present analysis was small, therefore the results obtained from the study might not be generalizable for the sub-Saharan African region. The study sample might under-represent professionals working in lower-level facilities, particularly in rural/village settings, as only few responses were received from these participants. This might be related to limited access to the internet in these settings. This is particularly relevant for the topic of this analysis, as we might underestimate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care because of the sample that was reached. Some cadres of professionals were also less represented (e.g., pediatricians and neonatologists).

In addition, analyzing just health workers' perspectives and experiences might fail to provide a complete picture of the true impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care, since the point of view of women was not represented. Coding and theme formation: coding of open-ended responses and formulation of themes was done by a single coder, instead of the recommended 2-3 coders. This might compromise the rigor and reliability of the coding process and content analysis. Translation restrictions: "Google translate" was used in the translation of "French free text" responses. The meaning of the text might be altered or lost by using automatic translate algorithms, losing accuracy.

5 Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic and its associated mitigation measures had both negative and positive impacts on the quality and continuum of maternal and newborn care provision in the sub-Saharan African region. The main negative impacts of the pandemic on antenatal and intrapartum care provision were decreased access to these services by women, while the main impacts on postnatal care provision were a decrease in the number of visitors permitted in inpatient postnatal wards, and an increase spacing of out-patient postnatal appointments. The main positive findings on the other hand were an enhancement of the infection prevention and the hygiene and sanitation measures at the health facilities and an adaptation of the health service delivery to suit the provision of care during the pandemic. There is therefore the need to strike a balance between implementing mitigating measures and ensuring the continuous delivery of quality maternal and newborn services during pandemics while improving health systems' resilience and preparedness to face subsequent health system shocks.

Operating theatre in a hospital maternity ward, Lagos, Nigeria. May 2022.

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